

DIACHRONY OF 'MANNER' VERBS**Mardonova Sitora Mardonovna**

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the semantic structure of some motion verbs in the English language, on the basis of which specific semantic events of the verbs of movement are determined. The main attention is paid to certain structures and boundaries of verbs, that is, the semantic field of verbs belonging to this group, and the semantic classification of lexemes of this group of verbs to identify their common, unifying, differentiating semantics. From this article we can see what the meanings of the verbs used in Old English to this day had, and by attaching grammatical forms to these verbs, some verbs acquired additional meanings. Verbs used during the period of Old English have been studied in different directions and the scope of their meaning has been analyzed. In some cases it had different meanings in different contexts.

Keywords: Diachronic, typology, meaning, semantics, form, space, verbs of action, differentiation, path verbs.

Introduction

Verbs expressing manner of motion stand out due to their codability. Compared to other types of motion verbs, they tend to be more highly codable, as they are more frequently used in their non-finite forms, occur independently rather than in fixed phrases or collocations, and possess a distinct lexical meaning. Codability refers to a verb's ability to combine with other linguistic units (such as adverbs and participles) and form a distinctive frame-based structure.

In Old English, most verbs expressing manner of motion denoted intransitive movement. For instance, the verb *hien* (meaning “to go quickly”) was used to indicate rapid forward motion, but it disappeared from usage by Middle English. Other Old English verbs denoting manner of movement include: *gogelen* (“to stagger”), *hurtelon* (“to stumble”), *poperen* (“to ride rapidly”), *stamyeren* (“to walk clumsily”), *flusshen* (“to move rapidly”), *hurlen* (“to rush quickly”), and *jumpen* (“to walk quickly”).

Additionally, Old English adopted certain verbs from High Germanic dialects, such as *blusteren* (“to stray blindly”), *shokken* (“to move rapidly”), and *trampen* (“to tread heavily”), which were widely used to express manner of motion. However, by the Middle English period, many of these Old English motion verbs had been replaced by French loanwords such as *to chase*, *to pursue*, *to hunt*, which quickly became integrated into English.

Materials and methods

Based on the analysis above, it can be concluded that many Old English manner-of-motion verbs were replaced by French borrowings in Middle English. Over time, internal linguistic changes led to the emergence of new motion verbs. According to T. Fanego, at the beginning of the Modern English period, 205 manner-of-motion verbs were identified, whereas by Late Modern English, this number had increased to 250¹. However, due to the emergence of new affixes and semantic expansions, the overall number of manner-of-motion verbs in Present-Day English has significantly decreased. As shown in the table (Table 4), motion verbs continue to hold a central position among intransitive verbs.

Table 4.

Comparative analysis of manner-of-motion verbs.

<i>Drēopan</i>	<i>Drepen</i>	<i>to Drip</i>
(to drop, drip)	(to drip, fall in drops,	(tomchilab tomish)

¹ Fanego T. Motion events in English: The emergence and diachrony of manner salience from Old English to Late Modern English. *Folia Linguistica Historica*, 2012. – P. 29-85.

to droop, sink down)		
<i>And swa fager dropa te on æas eorpan upon dreopap. And like the sweet drops that drop onto the earth..</i>	<i>þe woman for grete sorrow wepyd, þe terys oure hir face drepyd.</i>	<i>The woman wept with great sorrow, the tears dripped over her face.</i>
Dūfan (to dive or plunge into a liquid)	Duven (to plunge into water, dive to sink, fall down;)	Fall down (pastga tushish)
<i>Ac gedufan sceolun in pone deopan wælm. But they shall plunge into the deep fiery flame.</i>	<i>Wi þæt ilke beide & def duuelunge dun to æer eorpe sone bihefdet.</i>	<i>And at the same moment she bent and at once sank down headlong to the earth, beheaded.</i>
Feallan (to descend, drop, fall to become detached)	Fallen (to descend, drop, fall)	to Fall (tushmoq)
<i>And tar feoll adune swilce of pam hrofe wearm hlaf mid his syflinge. And there also fell down from the roof a warm loaf with food.</i>	<i>She swooned now..Til wel neigh is she fallen fro the tree.</i>	<i>Now she swooned, until she has almost fallen from the tree.</i>

Result and discussion

Based on historical analyses of the English language, T. Fanego states that speakers have used manner-of-motion verbs more frequently than path-motion verbs². However, distinguishing between manner-of-motion verbs and path-motion verbs can be quite challenging.

For instance, in examples 1 and 2, the verb "arrive" appears to function as a path-motion verb. In all three cases, the meaning of the verb is implicitly expressed.

For example:

² Fanego, Teresa., Motion events in English: The emergence and diachrony of manner salience from Old English to Late Modern English. *Folia Linguistica Historica* 2012. – P. 33– 85.

1. Tat folc of Denemarch aryuede in te Nort contreye

Translation: The people of Denmark arrived in the North country.

2. Nu beod of Brutaine beornes ariued i tis lond at Tottenas

Translation: The barons have arrived from Brittany into the land at Totnes.

3. Te wynde aryueu te sayles of vlixes and hys wandryng shippes in to te isle tere as Circe dwellet

Translation: The wind (makes) arrive the sails of Ulysses and his wandering ships into the island where Circe dwells.

In Old English, the verb "aryuede" functions as a path-motion verb in examples 1 and 2, whereas in example 3, it behaves as a non-directional verb.

This demonstrates that the limited aspectual properties of verbs help determine their manner-of-motion meaning. Notably, some motion verbs borrowed from German can be classified as manner-of-motion verbs due to the ambiguity in whether they express transitivity or path-motion meaning.

Additionally, the German auxiliary verb "haben" ("to have") played a role in forming manner-of-motion meanings when combined with main verbs. One of the primary manner-of-motion verbs in this context was "wandelen" ("to walk"). For example:

4. Ik heb heerlijk gewandeld. (Auxiliary verb: "hebben" – "to have")

Translation: I have lovely walked.

Meaning: I have had a great walk.

5. Ik ben daarheen gewandeld. (Auxiliary verb: "to be")

Translation: I am there to walked.

Meaning: I have walked there.

The similarities between Old and Modern English in the usage of manner-of-motion and path-motion verbs can be observed as follows.

In this case, we can observe manner-of-motion verbs in example 4, whereas path-motion verbs appear in example 6.

For example:

6. ðone widfarendan ænd ðone eæd on þin bus

Translation: And lead the wanderer and beggar into your house.

7. Cunuciað ænd eow bið geopenod

Translation: Knock, and the door will be opened.

According to T. Fanego, example 6 illustrates the syntactic structure of a motion verb³. In example 7, an abstract verb ("go") combines with a manner-of-motion verb to convey meaning.

For example:

8. þa hic ða hæfdon feorðan dæl þare ca geswummen

Translation: When they had swum a quarter of that river.

J. Zlatev examines both perspectives and highlights that in such cases, the motion verb "go" functions to express the state and purpose of the argument within the sentence⁴.

Now, let's analyze pure path-motion verbs used in Old English alongside path-motion verbs borrowed from Latin and French:

Initially, verbs expressing both direction and manner constituted 57% of the total motion verbs.

a) Speed-related verbs (total: 33):

arnan, blæstan, cleacian, drīfan, ef(e)stan / of(e)stan, fundian, fȳsan, hradian, irnan/ iernan/ rinnan/ yrnan, læcan, ðnettan, pleg(i)an, racian, ræsan, recan, scēon, scēotan, scotian, scūfan, scūdan, scyndan, snēowan, snyrian, st(i)ellan/ styllan, stincan, swengan, tengan, teran, tocerian, ringan.

b) Slow or impeded motion (sust harakat ma'nosida) (total: 8):

³ Fanego T. Motion events in English: The emergence and diachrony of manner salience from Old English to Late Modern English. *Folia Linguistica Historica* 2012. – P 45-85.

⁴ Zlatev J. Polysemy or generality? Cognitive approaches to lexical semantics. Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter. 2003. – P. 447– 94; Zlatev J. Spatial semantics. *The Oxford handbook of cognitive linguistics*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2007. – P. 318– 350; Zlatev J., Peerapat Y. A third way to travel: The place of Thai and serial verb languages in motion event typology. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, 2004. – P. 159–190.

crēopan, healtian, huncettan, luncian, slincan, smūgan, snīcan, tealtrian.

c) Movement through air or fluid (havo yoki suvdagi harakat) (total: 13):

dūfan, fi.ercian, fi.erian, flēogan, flēotan, flicerian/ flicorian, flogettan, floterian, flotian, lī.an, rōwan, siglan/ segl(i)an, swimman.

d) Falling (tushmoq) (total: 9):

drēopan, drēopian, drēosan, feallan, feallettan, gefetan, hrēosan, lūtan, sincan.

e) Gliding (parvoz harakati) (total: 9):

flōwan, glīdan, gelīsian, happan, sicerian, seohhian/ sēon, slīdan, slidrian, slūpan.

f) Jumping (sakramoq) (total: 6):

hlēapan, hlēapettan, hoppetan, hoppian, (wi.er)hyppan, springan.

g) Rolling (aylanmoq) (total: 7):

hwearfian, hwearftlian, hwierfan/ hwyrfan, turnian, tyrnan, trāwan, wealwian.

h) Fleeing, escaping (qochmoq) (total: 3):

gedīgan, flēon, sceacan/ scacan.

i) Other manner-of-motion verbs (harakat usulini ifodalovchi) (total: 22):

climban, crūdan, fētan, frician, lācan, rīdan, s(e)altian, spurnan, stappan, (be)stealcian, stalian, (be)stelan, swēgan, swōgan, tredan, treddan, treddian, treppan, tumbian, wealcan, weallan, windan.

2) Initially, verbs that primarily expressed path-motion accounted for 10% of all motion verbs:

a) Towards (bironbir yo‘nalish tomon) (total: 4):

grētan, lendan, genēahian, nēahlācan.

b) In (og‘rimoq) (total: 2):

innian, scipian.

c) Away (uzoq) (total: 5):

feorrian, feorsian/ fyrsian, (for)lāetan, wīcan, (ge)wītan.

d) Down (pastga tomon bo‘ladigan harakat) (total: 5):

gryndan, hnīgan, hyldan, līhtan, sīgan.

e) Up (yuqoriga bo‘ladigan harakatlar) (total: 2):

(a)rāēman, rīsan.

f) Through (aylanma harakat) (total: 1):

pattan.

g) Neutral motion verbs (neytral ma’noga ega bo‘lgan harakat fe’llari) accounted for 25% of all motion verbs.

būgan, cyrran/ cirran/ cierran, cuman, dragan, dwelian, dwelsian, dwolian, el.ēodgian, faran, fēolan, fēran, fercian, ferian, folgian, fylgan, gān, gangan, gengan, gēotan, hweorfan, lēoran, reccan, scrī.an, settan, sī.ian, spyrian, stīgan, strīcan, strīdan, styrian, swīcan, swician, swīfan, tēon, (wi.)tremman, .ragan, wadan, wandrian, warlan, wā.an, weallian, wegan, wendan, wōrian, wracian, wracnian, wrēcan, wrigian;

3) Initially, verbs that did not explicitly express motion accounted for 8% of all verbs.

Conclusion

The following verbs were identified: *berstan, brecan, (ge)dōn, facian, feohtan, healdan, hīgian, metan, nēosian, niman, (ā)redian, sēcan, slēan, weorðan, winnan*. These verbs exhibited a wide range of meanings in different texts.

The meanings of manner-of-motion verbs in Old English were more consciously stable compared to neutral motion verbs. However, by the Middle English period, some of these verbs had been replaced by French and Latin loanwords.

From the Middle English period onward, the semantics of motion manner became increasingly dependent on other linguistic elements within the context, such as postpositions, adverbs, and participles.

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